

NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING**Abdumurodov Asrorjon O'rol o'g'li**

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Abstract. This article reveals the unique benefits and effectiveness of using various new pedagogical technologies in teaching English. The article talks about the specific features of modern innovative technologies in teaching English. In addition, the increase in the demand for learning foreign languages in our country and the attention paid to it were specifically discussed and revealed with the help of examples.

Key words: new technologies, pedagogical, teacher- centred, pupil, innovations

НОВЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. В данной статье раскрываются уникальные преимущества и эффективность использования различных новых педагогических технологий в обучении английскому языку. В статье говорится об особенностях современных инновационных технологий в обучении английскому языку. Кроме того, конкретно обсуждалось и раскрывалось с помощью примеров повышение спроса на изучение иностранных языков в нашей стране и уделяемое ему внимание.

Ключевые слова: новые технологии, педагогический, ориентированный на учителя, ученик, инновации.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, for teaching English attention is increasing. With the spread and progress of English around the world, English is used as a second language in a country like India and for some people the 1st language. It enjoys a high esteem in the country. At present the role and status of English in India is higher than ever as evidenced by its bargain as a key subject of middling of instruction, prospectus. As the number of English learners is mounting odd teaching methods have been implemented to test the helpfulness of the teaching process. Use of authentic materials in the form of films, radio, TV has been there for a long time. It is true that these technologies have proved triumphant in replacing the long-established teaching. The new era assigns new challenges and duties on the modern teacher. The tradition of English instruction has been drastically changed with the noteworthy entry of technology. Technology provides so many options as construction teaching interesting and also making teaching more industrious in terms of improvements. Technology is utilized for the upliftment of recent styles; it satisfies both visual and auditory senses of the students.

THE FUTURE OF ENGLISH

The use of Multimedia Technology in Teaching As the popularity of English is expanding day by day and worldwide, the teachers of English feel the need of change in their tongue teaching methods. there are teachers who use the "foremost edge of technological and scientific development" (Young and Bush 2), but the majority of teachers still teach in the traditional

manner. However, this paper does not state that none of these traditional manners are bad or hurtful the students. In opinion, they are proving to be useful even today. there are many opportunities for students to gain confidence in erudition English who learn the speech for more than just fun. For them, to go on pace with English language teaching and put on more assurance, they have to stride into the world of multimedia technology. Here, multimedia technology refers to computer-based interactive applications that use both the hardware and software, allowing people to share their ideas and in turn. It is a mishmash of text, graphics, animation, video and sound. Twenty first century is the age of globalization and information technology as Harry Samuels argues, "Much more recent developments in social media and information technology are taking dialect education in new directions". English is one of the imperative mediums of communication in the world, so it is important to learn the language. As a result, English lingo teaching has been one of the important subjects in education. In fact, there are more non-native than native speakers of the language. With the rapid growth of science and technology, the use of multimedia technology in language teaching has created a complimentary context for reforming and exploring English language preparation models in the new age. This inclination features the use of audio, visual, and animation effects in the English language teaching classrooms. Multimedia technology plays a objector role in civilizing actions and initiatives of students and teaching end product in the classrooms. Thus, industrial innovations should Go hand in hand with the growth of English and change the way in which we Communicate. In fact, the growth of the Internet has facilitated the growth of the English language. In this astuteness, computers are no longer the exclusive domains of a few individuals, but rather they are available to many. Teachers can use multimedia technology to create more colorful and stimulating language program. There are many techniques applicable in different forms to English language teaching situations that now intimidate "to undermine the classroom completely as a position of study". Some are useful for testing and distance education; some for teaching business English, spoken English, reading, listening or interpreting. the attitude of teaching should be to comprehend new technologies without charming over the role of the teacher and without 1St National Conference on Teaching Innovations and Enhancing Learning. Most significantly, the new technologies have been showing and disseminated so quickly that we cannot avoid their attraction and authority on all of us: both teachers and learners, even both native and non-native speakers of English. Analysis on Necessity of Application of Multimedia Technology to English Teaching To Cultivate Students' Interest in Study Nowadays, the stereotyped traditional teaching methods and environment are unpopular while multimedia technology featuring audio, visual animation effects naturally and humanely makes us more access to information above and beyond, with such characteristics as abundant- information and crossing time and space, multimedia technology offers a sense of truth and functions very well, which greatly cultivates students' interest and motivation in study and their involvement in class activities. To Promote Students' Communication Capacity Traditional teaching has hampered students' capacity to figure out certain language and also understanding to configuration, meaning and function of the language, and makes the students passive recipients of knowledge, So it is hard to achieve the objective of communication. With teachers' directions foremost students' thought patterns and motivating students' emotions, the multimedia technology seeks incorporation of teaching and learning and provides the students greater incentives, The PPT

courseware activate students' thinking; the visual and brilliant courseware can help them to transform English learning into capability development. And such in-class activities as group discussion, subject discussion, and debates can also offer more opportunities for statement among students and between teachers and students. So multimedia technology teaching has uniquely stirred students' hopeful thinking and communication skills in social performance. To Improve Teaching Effect Multimedia teachings enrich coaching content and make the best of class time and break the "teacher-centered" teaching pattern and fundamentally improve class efficiency. Due to large classes it is tricky for the students to have speaking communication. The utilization of multi-media thus materializes the individualized and co-operative teaching. The traditional teaching model mainly emphasized on teachers' instruction, and the in sequence provided is limited due to traditional classes. On the divergent, multimedia technology goes beyond time and space, creates more vivid, visual, true environment for English learning, stimulates students' initiatives and economizes class time meanwhile increases class information. Widens Students' Knowledge about the Culture of English The use of multimedia technology, "connected to the target culture", offers the students with more information than textbooks, and helps them to be familiar with cultural backgrounds and real-life language materials, which can attract the students to learning. Having the profuse information through the use of multimedia technology, the students can be operational with knowledge about the ethnicity of the target language. This brings about an information sharing occasion among students and makes them actively participate in the class. Activities that help the students to learn the language more quickly and effectively. To Improve Interaction between Teacher and Student Multimedia teaching stresses the role of students, and enhances the importance of "interaction" amid teachers and students. A major feature of multimedia teaching is to prepare and improve students' ability to pay attention and speak, and to develop their communicative competence, During this process, the teacher's role as a facilitator is particularly prominent. Using multimedia in background manufacture creates a good platform for the exchange between teachers and students, while at the same time providing a language environment that improves on the traditional classroom teaching model. In this way, teachers in the classroom no longer blindly input in sequence and force students to receive it in a passive way. To Provide Flexibility to Course Content In adding up, multimedia teaching is also flexible. It is obvious that the context can be twisted not only in the classroom, but also after class. Multimedia language teaching can also create a multimedia language environment for the principle of conducting language teaching. English teaching itself must spotlight on the management of teachers and be student-centered, which we believe is one of the principles for language teaching. Students are hop to have some evils in classroom teaching, which can be addressed under the guidance of teachers. In such circumstances, students can use the new technology to their lead, such as manipulating the network to contact teachers, and receiving answers by email. Advantages of the Use As the multimedia technology becomes more readily available to all of us, it seems appropriate that the language teachers should integrate it into their lesson and appraisal scheduling in the same way they have been doing with video, Internet and computer assisted learning strategies. The students are surrounded by technology and this technology can provide interesting and new approaches to language teaching because "the use of technology for coaching and learning is moving their institution in the right direction". In this way, the teachers of English can take full advantage of technology to teach

English in the non-native communication countries. the following are some of the important advantages of the use of multimedia technology Develops Students' Communicative Competence It is hard to accomplish the goal of learning English language through the traditional teaching because it hampers the students' aptitude to recognize the structure, meaning and function of the language. Such teaching method makes the students 1St National Conference on Teaching Innovations and Enhancing

IMPROVES TEACHING EFFICIENCY

Using multimedia technology in the language classrooms improves teaching contents and makes the best of class time. It breaks the teacher-centered traditional teaching method and basically improves the teachers' teaching efficiency and has develop into "central to language practice". For large classes, it is difficult for the students to have speaking communication, but the utilization of multi-media sound laboratory materializes the face-to- face teaching. the traditional teaching techniques only highlight on teachers' training and provide limited information to the students. Provides Opportunities for English Teaching Outside the Classrooms Teaching English with multimedia technology is flexible that focuses on "how English language teachers, teacher educators, and administrators can and should use technology in and out of the classroom" (Healey et. al. 2). this means that multimedia technology provides opportunities to have English teaching not only with in the classroom situations, but also external the classroom situations. It creates a multimedia language situation for teaching English. Teaching should be handled by the teachers but it should be student-centered, which is one of the morality of good language teaching.

CONCLUSION

Concerning the progress of technology, we believe that in future, the use of multimedia English teaching will be added developed. The process of English learning will be more student-centered but less time-consuming. Therefore, it promises that the teaching quality will be improved and students' applied English skill look into be effectively cultivated, meaning that students' communicative competence will be further developed. In end, we believe that this process can fully get better students' ideation and practical language skills, which is supportive and useful to ensure and fulfill an effective result of teaching and learning.

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